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Characterization and Statistical Analysis of Single Fiber Strength of Fibers at Various Processing Stages

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Notre monde est textile

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Introduction, motivation and objectives

Composite failure mechanics

Weak-link theory

Why characterize single fibre:

- Failure in unidirectional organic composites, loaded longitudinally, usually originates within fibres. This makes **fibre failure kinetics a key parameter for failure modelling in composites**
- Composites are strongly overdesigned, one of the reason it must be done is because of **unreliability of the constituent properties such as fibres**
- For **critical applications such as pressure vessels** where failure models must predict absolute failure behaviour, SFT becomes more critical
- **Success of a stochastic model**, depends on correctly capturing fibre strength statistics and failure kinetics

Introduction, motivation and objectives

Objectives:

- Addressing the challenges for automatic characterization of carbon and glass fibers in single fibre tensile tests (SFT)
- Finding answer to the question: if the tensile strengths and Weibull parameter of fibers are altered at several processing stages
- Understanding experimental uncertainties and ideal distribution for single fiber testing

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Manual single fiber testing

Drawbacks:

- Time consuming (limiting Nr of tests)
- Uncertainties due to manual intervention
- Fiber-preselection effect
- Inaccurate cross-section measurement
- Effect of misalignment
- No gauge length correction
- Testing at shorter gauge lengths

Automated single fiber testing and distribution

- Strength of a single fibre cannot be captured in one single average value
- **Weibull lifetime distribution:** Useful for drawing conclusions on the general reliability of the specimens.
- Two types of Weibull distributions

$$P(\sigma_f) = 1 - \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{L}{L_0}\right)\left(\frac{\sigma_f - \sigma_u}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right\} \quad \text{or} \quad P(\sigma_f) = 1 - \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{L}{L_0}\right)\left(\frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right\}$$

L = Characteristic gauge length, L_0 = Reference gauge length, σ_f = Fibre strength
 σ_0 = Scale parameter, m = Shape parameter, and σ_u = Location parameter

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Fibers per 100 usable test results

Fibers per 100 fibers mounted on the cassette

Observation, results and discussion

Weibull	Sample	σ_0 [GPa]	m [-]	Nº fibres
2-P	From Bobbin	3,71	6,04	96
	From Spread tape	3,76	4,85	113
	From Fabric	3,8	6,07	101

Observation, results and discussion

Preselection effect!
+
Fibre breakages!

Weibull	Sample	σ_0 [GPa]	m [-]	Nº fibres
2-P	From Bobbin	2,88	5,23	92
	From Spread tape	2,83	6,18	96
	From Fabric	2,82	5,56	90

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Carbon fiber bobbin.
Each roving containing
approx. 12000 fibers

Carbon fiber UD spread
tape, made by combining
several rovings side by side

Carbon fiber UD NCF fabric
made by stitching the spread
tape by PET stitching thread

Conclusion

- Carbon fibre prominently shows preselection effect.
- Effect of processing on the strength of carbon/glass fibres and their distribution can be observed, but it is not very significant. For the current setting this effect can be discarded as the significance is lower than the uncertainties due to randomness.
- Glass fibres has very low preselection effect. The number of fibres not tested due to fibre extraction, mounting and testing uncertainties is comparatively lower for carbon fibres than glass fibres.
- Carbon and glass behave differently, for example for carbon, in the spread tape, the spread of tensile strengths is maximum while for glass fibres from spread tape, the spread of strength values is minimum. For carbon scale parameter slightly increasing trend, while for glass it shows a decreasing trend.

“Thank you everyone for your kind attention.”

FiBreMoD

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